

Multilevel management of irregular migration and return in the EU: new insights and data

The case of France

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This report examines the management of irregular migration and return in the case of France. It presents the legislative context and includes ongoing developments. This report puts forward law application and uses examples of implementation practices from the Region *Alpes-Provence-Côte d'Azur*, department of *Alpes Maritimes*, where irregular migration is a salient issue and an institutional concern. The analysis of implementation practices is based on interviews with the heads of relevant services at the Prefecture, at the French Office for Immigration and Integration, in contracted NGOs and with attorneys. To avoid direct identification of respondents, I am not giving details about the exact function and dates. Pieces of information gathered through interviews are summarized in English in the body of this chapter. The footnotes show the excerpts of interviews in the original language. The analysis about data does not build on interviews since the relevant respondents have not participated in the research process. The research process has also been too short (15 days in total) to allow for returning to respondents who have not accepted to participate in the first round of interviews.

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List of acronyms

AME: Aide Médical Urgent, Urgent Medical Aid
CESEDA : Code de l'entrée et du séjour des étrangers et du droit d'asile/Code of entry and residence of foreigners and of the asylum law.
CNDA: Cour Nationale du Droit d'Asile – National Court for Asylum Law
CRA: Centre de Rétention Administrative/Immigration Removal Centres
CSO: Civil Society Organizations

DDETS: Direction Départementale de l'Emploi, du Travail et des Solidarités

EMN: European Migration Network

EURA: EU Readmission Agreement

GUDA: Guichet Unique de Demande d'Asile – Asylum Application Office

OFII: Office Français de l'Immigration et de l'Intégration/The French Office for Immigration and Integration

OFPRA: Office Français de Protection des Réfugiés et Apatrides – French Office for the Protection of Refugees and Stateless Persons

OTL: Orders to Leave

Key remarks

- Data about OtL revoked and/or canceled should be included in the statistical information and should be part of the assessment of the return capacity. The return capacity tends to be assessed by comparing OtL and returnees. The case of France shows that the understanding of implementation logics and practices is crucial to make sense of return capacity. OtL might be considered measures of irregular migration. However, OtL might not be measures of irregular migrants that should be returned. OtL might be issued to irregular migrants who are unremovable. The automatic issuance of OtL to rejected asylum seekers or migrants whose permit has not been renewed is an issue of debate between the Ministry of Interior, the Prefecture and the judicial administrations, precisely because the OtL might be issued to unremovable irregular migrants.
Given the institutional architecture of France, the discretionary powers of the Prefet are authorized. After the adoption of the new law on immigration (*Projet de loi pour contrôler l'immigration et améliorer l'intégration*) in December 2023, the Ministry of the Interior is organizing a meeting with the Prefets to steer the implementation of the new law, although some of its provisions might be contested by the judicial authorities. These tensions about the implementation might be reflected in the day-to-day practices such as the issuance of OtL. These aspects should be included in the analysis of return capacity especially if return capacity is assessed by comparing OtL and returnees. The return capacity might be biased by an exaggerated/inappropriate use of OtL.
- The management of irregular migration and return needs to be addressed by considering the relational aspects of legislative policymaking and implementation. That means that the management of irregular migration and return depends also on decisions and actions of the judiciary and other countries, for judicial review and international cooperation. Examples include judicial review for detention, for the issuance of OtL, for the legislative policymaking. In a nutshell, ineffectiveness of returns might be due to the fact that certain decisions and actions do not fully comply with the judiciary reviews and recommendation and therefore are somehow meant to fail when contested.
- France provides statistics on the issuance of consular laissez passer to measure international cooperation. More details are needed in regards to the connection between the issuance of laissez passer and voluntary returns. The assesment of the role of international cooperation in achieving returns needs to take account of EU wide and bi-lateral non-standard forms of agreement which might be more effective in achieving returns.
- The role of detention in managing irregular migration and effecting returns could be established in a more accurate manner by providing data on the relationship between the lenght of detention and the achievement of returns. Data provided by civil society organizations in their annual reports suggest that the longer irregular migrants are held in detention, the less they will be removed. Returns tend to take place in the beginning of detention.

- National and European statistical categories and definitions, such as ‘returnees’, ‘voluntary return’, ‘assisted voluntary return’, ‘risk of absconding’ and so on, do not always overlap. For the sake of comparability, it is key to ascertain what categories and definitions actually mean in the national context. Let me give an example: do measures about returnees include irregular migrants who leave without having received an OtL? The risk is to bend the national reality to European categories and to provide faulty measurements as a result.
- The exiting from the irregular status via regularization is not directly connected to OtL. Regularized immigrants might not have received an OtL. Also, the desirability of regularization should be assessed because regularization might be seen as illegitimate or a ‘pull factor’. There is a dilemma between the desirability of regularization as a means to manage irregular migration and the concerns about migration that underline the views of regularization as a pull factor and an illegitimate practice.

Management of irregular migration and return at national and sub-national level

Legal framework

The domain of immigration is characterized by so-called rule-piling. The constant developments and modifications of laws, regulations, circulars make immigration management a fastly moving legal environment. In the case of France, on the 19th of December 2023, the Senat has adopted the proposal for a new law on immigration¹ (*Projet de loi pour contrôler l'immigration et améliorer l'intégration*). Some of the developments under analysis are included in this chapter. However, respondents on the ground consider that it is too early to seize the impacts of this new law on the management of irregular migration and return.

The French law regulating several aspects of immigration is the Code of entry and residence of foreigners and of the asylum law 'Code de l'entrée et du séjour des étrangers et du droit d'asile'², also referred to as CESEDA.

Several actors and organizations are involved in the management of irregular migration, including:

- The French Office for Immigration and Integration (OFII - Office Français de l'Immigration et de l'Intégration) : OFII participates in the management of voluntary return and reintegration.
- The Prefecture: it is the local branch of the central government and represents the State at a local level. The Prefecture issues the Orders to Leave and is involved in administrative procedures for residence permits, including different forms of regularizations. The Prefecture registers asylum applications and is notified of rejections.
- Centre de Rétention Administrative (CRA - Immigration Removal Centres). (to manage irregular migrants and enforce returns)
- Police (relevant for checks on immigration statuses)
- Border Guards – relevant for refusal of entry

The CESEDA provides for the main instrument to identify and manage irregular migrants namely the *Obligation de Quitter le Territoire Français* (OQTF), which I will name Orders to Leave (OtL).

¹ Available at <https://www.senat.fr/leg/pjl23-224.html>

²https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/section_lc/LEGITEXT000006070158/LEGISCTA000006134411?isAbrogated=true#LEGISCTA000032171795

Pursuing Articles L611-1 to L611-3 of the CESEDA (latest version accessed on the 23rd of November 2023), OtL are issued in the following situations:

- Non-French nationals who cannot prove their regular entry on the French territory and without a regular permit of stay or whose permit has expired. This includes visa overstaying or overstaying the three months of authorized stay for those nationalities which are not submitted to visa requirements;
- Non-French nationals whose permit's renewal has been rejected or whose permit has been withdrawn;
- Asylum seekers, whose applications have been rejected, and appeal rights are exhausted (but see the note on OTL and asylum procedures here-after).
- Non-French nationals who have lived in France for more than three months without a regular permit and represent a threat for public order.

A note on OtL and asylum procedures

Asylum applications must be registered at the GUDA (Guichet Unique de Demande d'Asile – Asylum Application Office), located at the Prefecture, and then filed and processed at the OFPRA (Office Français de Protection des Réfugiées et Apatrides – French office for the protection of refugees and stateless persons). OFPRA's negative decisions might be appealed at the CNDA (Cour nationale du droit d'asile – national court for the right to asylum).

The option of issuing an OtL after a negative decision of the OFPRA (first instance) has been used in case of 'safe third countries'. This issue is extremely complex and has resulted in a number of courts decisions contesting the issuance of OtL in those cases³. The current situation shows that whereas the right to stay during the processing of asylum applications by the CNDA is maintained, the Prefet has a discretionary power in maintaining this right to stay. The issuance of an OtL for negative decisions in first instance is often contested because those decisions can be revoked by the CNDA. In 2022, the CNDA has revoked the 22% of negative decisions in first instance and has granted protection (2021, 21% - 2020, 24% - 2019, 21%)⁴. After a negative decision of the CNDA, an asylum seeker might appeal to the Conseil d'État. This appeal does not grant a right to stay. So, an OtL might be issued after a negative decision of the CNDA.

³ For an in-depth analysis of these legal issues, see <https://www.actu-juridique.fr/administratif/contentieux-administratif/droit-des-etrangers-non-loqtf-post-ofpra-nest-pas-automatique/> (last accessed on the 23rd of November).

⁴ Source: Author's elaboration on the basis of the official national data available at: <https://www.immigration.interieur.gouv.fr/fr/Info-ressources/Etudes-et-statistiques/Chiffres-cles-sejour-visas-cloignements-asile-acces-a-la-nationalite/Les-chiffres-2022-publication-annuelle-parue-le-22-juin-2023>

Current situation: A negative decision of the CNDA (second instance) *should* be followed by the issuance of the OtL. The new law contains a clear reference to this matter. It imposes to the Prefets to issue an OtL after a negative decision in second instance.

Implementation practices at the local level: To shed light on implementation practices, I took the case of the department *Alpes Maritimes* in the *Alpes-Provence-Côte d'Azur* region and questioned the implementation on the ground. The interview with the head of the migrants' service of one of the major NGOs involved in asylum reception and legal support for migrants and asylum seekers has revealed some patterns of practices. This NGO is one of the four NGOs contracted by the local prefecture to provide services (accommodation, legal counseling and legal support) linked to asylum and irregularity. According to this local practitioner, the issuance of an OtL at the final rejection of asylum claims is not automatic⁵. If rejected asylum seekers refuse to leave the accommodation provided, the police will force them to leave. However, that does not automatically entails the issuance of an OtL⁶.

As shown in the section 'Available measures of irregular migration', France issues the highest numbers of OtL in the EU (see Table 3). We could make the hypothesis that although OtL are issued, a person might be unremovable. That might explain the high numbers of OtL that France issues when compared to other EU Member States.

(see Eurostat https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title>Returns_of_irregular_migrants_-_quarterly_statistics).

Interviews show that the issuance of OtL is also shaped by the judicial administration. The head of a relevant service at the Prefecture *Alpes-Maritimes* has explained that the issuance of OtL should not be automatic, according to the administrative judge. Before issuing an OtL, the Prefecture should analyse the case in depth and assess whether there are reasons for the person to appeal to the OtL. In most cases, these reasons relate to the length of residency in France or family ties in France⁷. This respondent has evoked a report by the *Conseil d'Etat* (the highest

⁵ Ce n'est pas automatique. En tout cas, ici, sur le 06 (Department Alpes-Maritimes), je ne sais pas ailleurs, ici, ce n'est pas automatique (Respondent 1, recorded interview).

⁶ Les policiers, ils leur demandent, sortez de l'appartement, ils vérifient que l'appartement on a bien changé les serrures et c'est tout. Ils les laissent partir. Ils ne les raccompagnent pas à la frontière. Ils ne les raccompagnent pas au CRA (detention centre). Et si on leur dit, mais pourquoi vous ne les raccompagnez pas ? Ils vont nous dire, on n'a pas reçu l'ordre, on n'a pas d'OQTF, on n'a pas d'ordre de les amener en CRA, on n'a pas le temps de les amener à la frontière, on n'a pas d'OQTF de toute façon, donc pourquoi on va les amener à la frontière ? (Respondent 1, recorded interview).

⁷ Le juge administratif, comment je dirais, ne veut pas de mesure automatique. C'est-à-dire qu'il dit bien on ne peut pas prendre une mesure stéréotypée. Vous êtes débouté du droit d'asile, tac, tac, tac, pouf, je signe, hop, voilà. En fait, il nous demande bien à chaque fois, à chaque mesure, de regarder quand même quelle est la... Quelle est la présence, la durée de présence en France. (Respondent 2, recorded interview).

administrative court) outlining those concerns⁸. The consequence of automatic issuance of OtL might be the increase of appeal procedures and backlog for administrative courts. I have not found data about revoked OtL so far (both at national and local levels).

Current legal context:

Pursuing Article L611-3 of CESEDA, the persons in the following situations cannot be subjected to a decision that implies the obligation to leave the French territory:

- Minors (unless the persons in charge of a minor have received an OtL)
- A lawful resident: you have had documents authorizing your residency in France for more than 20 years
- A lawful resident for more than 10 years (excluding students' permits of stay)
- Somebody who can prove that s/he has lived in France since s/he was a child (before s/he turned 14)
- Somebody who has been married to a French citizen for at least 3 years (you have been living together since your marriage and your spouse must have kept the French citizenship)
- Somebody who has been a legal resident for more than 10 years and has been married for at least 3 years to a foreigner who has been living in France since s/he was 13 years old (the person is not polygamous and has had a 'shared life', *vie commune*, since s/he got married)
- Somebody who is the mother or the father of a French minor child who lives in France (the person cannot be polygamous and must have supported the child since s/he was born or since at least 2 years)
- Somebody who benefits from a work accident or occupational disease pension from a French organization for a permanent incapacity rate of at least 20%
- Somebody who usually reside in France and whose state of health requires care in France, which cannot be accessed in the country of return⁹

⁸ Je crois que c'est le Conseil d'État, qui avait rendu tout un rapport sur le droit du séjour en France, l'immigration, disait qu'on devrait avoir un examen à 360 degrés pour ce genre de demandes de séjour. Mais pour éviter aussi qu'après, qu'il y a des recours, des... Bien sûr, oui, oui. Voilà. Donc, en fait, l'objectif, c'est que quand même quand on prend une décision, on a vérifié que la personne n'a effectivement pas de droit au séjour. (Respondent 2, recorded ointerview).

⁹ Instructions based on art. L611-3 of CESEDA and published on the official website of French public administration. Available at : <https://www.service-public.fr/particuliers/vosdroits/F18362#:~:text=Toutefois%2C%20l%27administration%20ne%20peut,pouvez%20être%20éloigné%20avec%20eux>

Toutefois, **l'administration ne peut pas vous obliger à quitter la France** si vous vous trouvez dans l'une des situations suivantes :

- Vous êtes mineur (si vos parents font l'objet d'une telle mesure, vous pouvez être éloigné avec eux)
- Vous *séjournerez régulièrement*: *Situation d'un étranger en possession des documents l'autorisant à demeurer sur le territoire français* en France depuis plus de 20 ans

The new law also proposes to authorize the return of immigrants with regular permits, including those meeting the conditions about residency and family ties described above, who have committed crimes punished with at least ten years of prison or five years in special circumstances. The law also proposes to authorize the obligation to leave the territory for irregular migrants who represent a serious threat for public order even in the case that these persons have personal and family ties in France like those listed above.

Practices to identify irregular migrants

The practices that allow for identifying irregular migrants and issuing an OtL are numerous. These practices are not systematically listed but can be identified by building on reports of civil society organizations (CSOs) that work in immigration detention centres¹⁰. These statistics are not exhaustive. They include conditions of apprehension of irregular migrants only before being placed in immigration detention centres. Table 1 shows the rate of apprehension per identification practice within the population of immigration detainees.

-
- Vous séjournez régulièrement en France depuis plus de 10 ans (sauf si vous avez été titulaire pendant toute cette période d'un titre de séjour *étudiant*)
 - Vous pouvez justifier par tous moyens résider habituellement en France depuis que vous êtes enfant (mais vous ne devez pas avoir commencé à y résider seulement à compter de votre 14e anniversaire)
 - Vous êtes marié depuis au moins 3 ans avec un Français (votre vie commune ne doit pas avoir cessé depuis votre mariage et votre époux doit avoir conservé la nationalité française)
 - Vous séjournez régulièrement en France depuis plus de 10 ans et êtes marié depuis au moins 3 ans avec un étranger vivant lui-même en France depuis au plus l'âge de 13 ans (vous ne devez pas être polygame et votre vie commune ne doit pas avoir cessé depuis votre mariage)
 - Vous êtes père ou mère d'un enfant français mineur résidant en France (vous ne devez pas être polygame et devez contribuer à l'entretien et à l'éducation de votre enfant depuis sa naissance ou depuis au moins 2 ans)
 - Vous bénéficiez d'une rente d'accident du travail ou de maladie professionnelle d'un organisme français pour un taux d'incapacité permanente de minimum **20 %**
 - Vous résidez habituellement en France et votre état de santé nécessite des soins en France, auxquels vous ne pourriez pas accéder dans le pays de renvoi

¹⁰ Annual Report 'Centre et locaux de rétention administrative' (2022 and 2021). Available at: <https://www.lacimade.org/publication/rapport-2022-sur-les-centres-et-locaux-de-retention-administrative/>

Table 1 Weight of identification practice within immigration detainees (2021-2022).

	2021	2022
Police ID check (general and in streets)	22.47%	38.2%
End of prison sentence	23.54%	26.6%
Apprehension at the prefecture	13.64%	9.3%
Border apprehension	7.55%	6%
Road police check	6.96%	5.1%
Rail Station check	6.11%	4.3%
Apprehension after police check (people placed in residencies before expulsions)	2.55%	2.5%
Apprehension at home	2.81%	2.4%

Transfer from EU MS	1.4%	1.1%
Police headquarter convocation	1.38%	1.1%
Public transport	1.22%	0.9%
Work place	1.1%	0.8%
Courts	N/A	0.4%
Exit from international zone	N/A	0.4%
Others	N/A	0.8%

Source : Annual Report ‘Centre et locaux de rétention administrative’ (2022 and 2021). Available at: <https://www.lacimade.org/publication/rapport-2022-sur-les-centres-et-locaux-de-retention-administrative/>

The major sources of identification of irregular migrants involve police checks (ID checks, rail stations, roads rather than workplaces) and apprehensions at the prefecture, within the frame of administrative procedures.

Detention

A person can be kept in detention for maximum 90 days. Decisions to detain are made by the *Prefet* and submitted for judicial control by the *Juge des libertés et de la detention* (after 48h, after 30 days, after 45 days, after 70 days, after 90 days¹¹). It is a judge of the judicial court (*tribunal judiciaire*). According to the head of a relevant service at the *Prefecture*, the judicial review about decisions to detain irregular migrants concern the assessment of the so-called *garantie de representation*, meaning that detention might be justified when an address of residency or the presence

¹¹ LOI n°2011-672 du 16 juin 2011 relative à l’immigration, à l’intégration et à la nationalité (Official publication: Journal Officiel de la République Française (JORF) ; Publication date: 2011-06-17) Décret no 2011-820 du 8 juillet 2011 pris pour l’application de la loi no 2011-672 du 16 juin 2011 relative à l’immigration, à l’intégration et à la nationalité et portant sur les procédures d’éloignement des étrangers (Official publication: Journal Officiel de la République Française (JORF); Publication date: 2011-07-09)

of family members cannot be established or if the person represents a threat to public order¹². This respondent has claimed that one could name that process ‘the assessment of the risk of absconding’, given that they do not adopt that terminology. In detention, assisted voluntary return cannot be proposed as an option to return.

The Return Directive has been transposed into French law with the *LOI n°2011-672 du 16 juin 2011 relative à l’immigration, à l’intégration et à la nationalité* (Official publication: Journal Officiel de la République Française (JORF); Publication date: 2011-06-17) and by the *Décret no 2011-820 du 8 juillet 2011 pris pour l’application de la loi no 2011-672 du 16 juin 2011 relative à l’immigration, à l’intégration et à la nationalité et portant sur les procédures d’éloignement des étrangers* (Official publication: Journal Officiel de la République Française (JORF); Publication date: 2011-07-09)

Cooperation with third-countries

Key fact: France is the top country for the numbers of bi-lateral agreements linked to readmission, as shown below:

¹² Parce que vous n’êtes pas en détention, vous n’êtes qu’un retenu. Mais effectivement, c’est une privation de liberté, quelque part. Et donc, là, vous êtes soumis au contrôle du juge des libertés de la détention. Oui, oui, oui. D’abord, qui vérifie si effectivement la personne, est-ce que c’est bien justifié qu’elle soit dans ce centre de rétention. Et c’est là où on va nous dire, ben prouvez qu’il n’y a pas de garantie de représentation, c’est un régime. Voilà. Donc ça, on a des contrôles, alors au bout de 48 heures, puis au bout de 30 jours, puis au bout de 45 jours, puis au bout de 70 jours, 90 jours, etc. Donc ça, il y a un contrôle vraiment très régulier du juge. (...) Des garanties de représentation, ça veut dire qu’on estime qu’elles ne vont pas...Elles risquent de...Ce que vous appelez le risque de fuite. Pas vraiment de domicile connu. Pas vraiment de famille. Ou en tout cas, c’est pas très clair. Ou il y a une forte menace à l’ordre public, etc.

Figure 1: Numbers of bi-lateral agreements linked to readmission stipulated by the 27 EU Member States (reproduced from Jean Pierre Cassarino – jeanpierrecassarino.com/datasets/ra/)

A description of the types of bi-lateral agreements sheds light on the importance of standard and non-standard bi-lateral return agreements, either linked or not linked to EURAs.

Standard readmission agreements include:

- Bilateral readmission agreements which may be signed or have entered into force;
- Bilateral Implementing Protocols to EU readmission agreements (EURAs), concluded between an EU Member State and a non-EU country;
- Agreements concluded between the Benelux countries and a third country.

Non-standard agreements include:

police cooperation agreements, including a clause on the readmission/removal of irregular foreigners;
Conventions including a clause on the readmission/removal of irregular foreigners; Memoranda of understanding;
Administrative arrangements;
Provisional agreements;
Exchanges of letters.

Appendix 1 shows the list of France's bi-lateral agreements specifying types of agreement and countries involved.

Appendix 2 shows the list of EU non-standard agreements linked to readmission. These agreements are EU-wide deals based on reciprocal commitments between the EU and its Member States, on the one hand, and a third country, on the other. Cooperation is aimed at dealing, among others, with readmission and with readmission-related issues, in the short- to long-term.

EU non-standard agreements include:

Mobility Partnership;
Common Agenda on Migration and Mobility;
Joint Way Forward;
Joint Declaration on Migration Cooperation;
Joint Statement;
Standard Operating Procedure for the identification and return of persons without an authorization to stay;
Good Practices for the efficient operation of the return procedure;
Admission Procedures for the return of foreign nationals from European Union Member States; Joint Migration Declaration;
Negotiations.

In Eurostat, data about returns per type of EURAs are not available for France¹³.

Below, I list the agreements that exist between France and the countries whose nationals provide the highest numbers of returnees (see Table 4).

Albania: EURA

¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/migr_eirt_agr_custom_8595782/default/table?lang=en

Algeria (lowest in-time issuing rate of *laissez-passer* – see Table 6):

Exchanges of letters 1984/1994; Signed Police cooperation agreements including a clause on the readmission/removal of irregular foreigners 25/10/2003 –

Negotiating Mandate of EURA since 2002.

Morocco:

Exchange of Letters 1983/1993; Entered-into-force Police cooperation agreements including a clause on the readmission/removal of irregular foreigners 01/05/2001;

Signed Convention including a clause on the readmission/removal of irregular foreigners (unaccompanied minors) 07/12/2020.

EU Mobility Partnership 07/06/2013.

Negotiating Mandate of EURA since 2002.

Tunisia:

Exchange of Letters 1984/1994; Entered-into-force Pact on joint migration management 01/07/2009.

EU Mobility Partnership 03/03/2014

Negotiating Mandate of EURA since 2014. Tunisia signed on 16th July 2023 a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) on a strategic and global partnership with the European Union. The MoU is not a readmission agreement. Readmission constitutes, however, a key aspect of the deal.

Afghanistan:

Signed Memorandum of Understanding 28/09/2002 with UNHCR; entered into force (18/09/2019) agreement part of the 2017 EU-Afghanistan Cooperation and Partnership Development Agreement.

02/10/2016 Joint Way Forward ; 26/04/2021 Joint Declaration on Migration Cooperation

Ivory Coast (highest in-time issuing rate of *laissez-passer* – see Table 7):

Negotiations for Standard Operating Procedure for the identification and return of persons without an authorization to stay. Good Practices for the efficient operation of the return procedure (1/10/2018).

Statistical description of the context

Available measures of irregular migration

Irregular migration: by definition, irregular migration is difficult to measure. In the case of France, one measure concerns the urgent medical aid (AME - Aide Médical Urgent), since it can be used only by irregular migrants who meet specific requirements. Irregular migrants need to prove their identity and the stability of their residence in France by showing an entry visa or a bill. In some cases, migrants are asked to provide a tax statement or a renting statement. Academic research has shown that frontline workers might require more documents than those necessary, since they might be uncertain about the type of document that decision-makers need¹⁴. Irregular migrants also need to declare their resources, which the frontline officers might assess by asking questions about their lifestyle. The obtention of urgent medical aid depends on a certain level of revenues (not over 9,041€ per year as of the 1st of April 2021). Using the urgent medical aid as a measure of irregular migration is not considered to be reliable. Not all irregular migrants meet the requirements to obtain it. Not all eligible irregular migrants are aware of its existence. The survey *Premier Pas*, carried out by the Institute for Research and Information in Health Economics has shown that only 51% of those eligible for the urgent medical aid actually apply for it¹⁵. The little awareness about the existence of this aid constitute the main argument used to counter the hypothesis about urgent medical aid as a pull factor of migration. Table 2 shows the amount of urgent medical aid granted, as a proxy for the measure of irregular migration.

Table 2: Recipients of Urgent Medical Aid

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Recipients of Urgent Medical Aid	315,800	314,586	335,483	368,890	376,108

¹⁴ See L'aide médical d'État, la fabrique d'un faux problème. Available at : <https://www.icmigrations.cnrs.fr/defacto/defacto-031/>

¹⁵ <https://www.irdes.fr/recherche/enquetes/premiers-pas/actualites.html>

BÉNÉFICIAIRES DE L'AME

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2021/ 2020
Bénéficiaires de L'AME*	315 800	314 586	335 483	368 890	376 108	+ 2,0%

* Observation au 31 décembre pour 2016 et 2017, au 30 septembre ensuite

Source: CNAMTS

Champ: France

Source: <https://www.immigration.interieur.gouv.fr/Info-ressources/Etudes-et-statistiques/Chiffres-cles-sejour-visas-eloignements-asile-acces-a-la-nationalite/Les-chiffres-cles-de-l-immigration-2021> Last accessed: 09/10/2023

Reliable statistics about irregularity are those about the issuance of OtL, shown hereafter:

Table 3 Evolution of Orders to Leave (2008-2022)

Source: Knowledge Centre on Migration and Demography <https://migration-demography-tools.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dashboards/eu-migration-return-msc-and-sacs-perspective>
 Last accessed: 12/10/2023

Key fact: In 2022 and in the first quarters of 2023, France has been the top EU country for issued OtL. It has issued 3 or 4 times more OtL than the second EU country (Germany).

Source : Eurostat https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title>Returns_of_irregular_migrants_-_quarterly_statistics Last accessed: 11/10/2023

I could not verify the availability of national data about suspension or revocation of OtL and the national data about OTL, since the relevant respondents have not accepted to participate in this research.

Implementation practices at the local level (Region *Alpes-Provence-Cote d'Azur*, Department *Alpes Maritimes*): Local respondents have claimed that the prefecture does not issue the OtL systematically. Given the lack of resources, it does so when the irregular migrant is considered to be a danger for the society¹⁶.

Main nationalities covered by OtL:

From 2010 to 2022: Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia and Albania are the main non-EU nationalities covered by an OtL.

It is important to look at these figures having in mind the larger picture of immigration in France. Algerians, Moroccans and Tunisians have always represented a large share of the non-EU immigrant population in France. In 2021, they were the top three nationalities of newcomers (Source: International Migration Outlook, OECD, 2023¹⁷).

One might make the hypothesis that travel facilitations (such as Mobility Partnerships) underline the salience of these nationalities, as if travel facilitations increased the risk of irregular migration automatically. However, Algerians, Moroccans and Tunisians are submitted to visa requirements. The visa rejection rates for those countries are among the highest for France (see visa statistics for Schengen consulate¹⁸).

¹⁶ La préfecture de Nice elle n'édié des OQTF que quand elle estime que la personne est dangereuse sur le territoire, donc elle veut vraiment que cette personne soit mise en dehors du territoire, mais elle ne le fait pas pour 100% des cas où elle devrait édié une OQTF parce qu'elle n'a pas la capacité à le faire en termes de temps, de ressources humaines, d'argent, de budget. (...) Si on ne fait pas partie de l'asile, c'est qu'on est en situation irrégulière, on se fait arrêter par la police dans la rue, et le policier, il est très professionnel, et il ne nous dit pas « Passe ton chemin parce que je n'ai pas envie d'écrire de procédure aujourd'hui ». Il nous amène à la station de police, il constate qu'on est en situation irrégulière, il transmet à la préfecture, et la préfecture, décide d'édié une OQTF. Ça, ça se passe très rarement, puisque la police va plutôt dire « Passe ton chemin, moi, écrire dix feuilles de paperasse ». Alors que, en fait, ce qui désespère la police, c'est que, même s'ils font édié, même s'ils arrivent à obtenir une OQTF, pour la faire appliquer, c'est...pour qu'il y ait une OQTF, ça veut dire que la personne, elle a commis un délit ou un crime, elle a été punie par la justice, et on veut être sûre qu'elle sort du territoire français. (Respondent 1, xx xx 202x).

¹⁷ https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/b0f40584-en/1/3/6/14/index.html?itemId=/content/publication/b0f40584-en&_csp_=f32aa69b63450530407ffa5853cb88a4&itemIGO=oecd&itemContentType=book

¹⁸ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/schengen-borders-and-visa/visa-policy/statistics-short-stay-visas-issued-schengen-states_en

As shown in Table 7 below, Algerians, Moroccans, Tunisians are not the main nationalities of asylum seekers. Albanians emerge as asylum seekers, although they are not among the top nationalities.

Key facts:

Algeria is the top country in 2010 and then from 2014 to 2022. Algeria has accounted for approximately 10% of the total OtL from 2010 to 2015, between 11% and 12% from 2016 to 2019 and then the figure has grown from 14.7% (2020) to 16.7% (2021) to 20.1% (2022).

Tunisia is the top country from 2011 to 2013, accounting for 18%, 12.7% and 10.7% of the total amount of OtL. A huge increase has existed between 2010 (only 7.2%) and 2011 (18%). This might be related to the so-called spring revolution in the country. From 2015 onwards, the share of OtL stabilizes around 6%-7%.

Morocco's share of OtL has been stable and ranges from 10% to 7% of the total amount of OtL.

Albania appears in statistics as a significant share of OtL only after 2013. From 2014 to 2019, the percentage has been growing from 5.2% to 8.8%. From 2020 to 2022, the percentage has decreased from 6.2% to 4.1% to 5.2%.

Source: Knowledge Centre on Migration and Demography <https://migration-demography-tools.jrc.ec.europa.eu/dashboards/eu-migration-return-msc-and-sacs-perspective>
Last accessed: 12/10/2023

Main nationalities of returnees:

The available national data on the nationalities of returnees cover the years 2018, 2021 and 2022, as shown in Table 4:

Nationalité	2018
ALBANAISE	3 115
ROUMAINE	2 182
ALGERIENNE	1 866
MAROCAINE	1 443
TUNISIENNE	974
SOUDANAISE	894
GUINEENNE	590
AFGHANE	562
GEORGIENNE	531
PAKISTANAISE	407
Total général	19 957
Part des 10 nationalités	63,0%

Nationalité	2021
ALBANAISE	1 832
ROUMAINE	1 229
MAROCAINE	844
GEORGIENNE	778
ALGERIENNE	754
AFGHANE	728
TUNISIENNE	621
GUINEENNE	549
MOLDAVE	390
MALIENNE	297
Total général	13 403
Part des 10 nationalités	59,9%

Nationalité	2022	2022/ 2021
ALBANAISE	2 249	+ 22,8 %
ALGERIENNE	1 876	+ 148,8 %
ROUMAINE	1 132	- 7,9 %
GEORGIENNE	980	+ 26,0 %
MAROCAINE	945	+ 12,0 %
TUNISIENNE	785	+ 26,4 %
GUINEENNE	653	+ 0,2 %
AFGHANE	576	- 20,9 %
IVOIRIENNE	298	+ 17,3 %
PAKISTANAISE	284	+ 2,2 %
Total général	15 400	+ 14,9 %
Part des 10 nationalités	63,5%	3,6 pts

Source : DGEF/DSED-DCPAF
Champ : France métropolitaine, tous pays, majeurs

Table 4 Nationalities of Returnees

Source: <https://www.immigration.interieur.gouv.fr/fr/Info-ressources/Etudes-et-statistiques/Chiffres-cles-sejour-visas-eloignements-asile-acces-a-la-nationalite/Les-chiffres-2022-publication-annuelle-parue-le-22-juin-2023>

In French national data, returnees include also irregular migrants who have returned without receiving an OtL (see section on Return). If we take for granted that all returnees listed in Table 4 have returned following an OtL, we can establish the following key facts (summarized in Table 5).

Key facts:

The top nationality of returnees is the Albanian.

In 2018, Albanians have received 8,930 OtL. Therefore, 34% of Albanians who have received an OtL have been returned. (42% on Eurostat data)

In 2021, Albanians have received 5,335 OtL. Therefore, 34% of Albanians who have received an OtL have been returned. (36% on Eurostat data)

In 2022, Albanians have received 7,105 OtL. Therefore, 32% of Albanians who have received an OtL have been returned. (33% on Eurostat data).

Another nationality of interest is the Algerian, mainly because it is the top nationality for OtL.

In 2018, Algerians have received 13,510 OtL. Therefore, 14% of Algerians who have received an OtL have been returned. (13% on Eurostat data)
In 2021, Algerians have received 20,920 OtL. Therefore, 4% of Algerians who have received an OtL have been returned. (3% on Eurostat data)
In 2022, Algerians have received 27,295 OtL. Therefore, 7% of Algerians who have received an OtL have been returned. (8% on Eurostat data).

Other nationalities that account for large numbers of OtL: Tunisians and Moroccans

Tunisians:

In 2018, Tunisians have received 6,650 OtL. Therefore, 15% of Tunisians who have received an OtL have been returned. (12% on Eurostat data)
In 2021, Tunisians have received 8,280 OtL. Therefore, 7.5% of Tunisians who have received an OtL have been returned. (10% on Eurostat data)
In 2022, Tunisians have received 10,265 OtL. Therefore, 8% of Tunisians who have received an OtL have been returned. (9% on Eurostat data).

Moroccans:

In 2018, Moroccans have received 8,340 OtL. Therefore, 17% of Moroccans who have received an OtL have been returned. (11% on Eurostat data)
In 2021, Moroccans have received 9,580 OtL. Therefore, 10% of Moroccans who have received an OtL have been returned. (6% on Eurostat data)
In 2022, Moroccans have received 10,490 OtL. Therefore, 9% of Moroccans who have received an OtL have been returned. (7% on Eurostat data)

Table 5 National and Eurostat data on OtL an return rates

	Number of OtL (Eurostat)	Number of returnees (National data)	Return Rate (Eurostat)	Return Rate (National data)
Albanians				
• 2018	8,930	3,115	42%	34%
• 2021	5,335	1,832	36%	34%
• 2022	7,105	2,249	33%	32%
Algerians				
• 2018	13,510	1,866	13%	14%
• 2021	20,920	754	3%	4%
• 2022	27,295	1,876	8%	7%
Tunisians				
• 2018	6,650	974	12%	15%
• 2021	8,280	621	10%	7.5%
• 2022	10,265	785	9%	8%
Moroccans				
• 2018	8,340	1,443	11%	17%
• 2021	9,580	844	6%	10%
• 2022	10,490	945	7%	9%

Sources: Eurostat https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title>Returns_of_irregular_migrants_-_quarterly_statistics

<https://www.immigration.interieur.gouv.fr/fr/Info-ressources/Etudes-et-statistiques/Chiffres-cles-sejour-visas-eloignements-asile-acces-a-la-nationalite/Les-chiffres-2022-publication-annuelle-parue-le-22-juin-2023>

Table 5 shows discrepancies between Eurostat and national data. There are discrepancies about the number of returnees, and this can be verified because the number of returnees is available in national data and it can be calculated on the basis of Eurostat data. There might be a discrepancy

between data about OtL, but national data on OtL were not made available. I could not verify those discrepancies, since the relevant respondents have not accepted to participate in this research.

Statistical data about how (forced) returns are linked to agreements with third countries are not publicly available in national data. However, France produced statistics about the consular cooperation on the issuance of *laissez-passer consulaires* following recognitions of nationality (2017-2021), as shown in Table 6:

Table 6 Consular Laissez-passer

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Laissez-passer requested	5,811	7,499	8,356	4,685	5,474
Laissez-passer issued in time	2,966	4,028	5,610	2,619	2,941
Laissez-passer issued but late	147	243	164	139	198
Laissez-passer rejected	314	415	237	149	178
Unanswered request	2,384	2,813	2,345	1,778	2,157
In-time issuance rate	51%	53,7%	67,1%	55,9%	53,7%

Table 7: Consular laissez-passer per nationality

	Return decisions	Returns executed*	Laissez-passer requested	Rate of nationality recognition	In-time issuing rate
Algeria	21,452	754	927	51,7%	5,8%
Morocco	9,701	844	775	62,3%	43,1%
Tunisia	8,446	621	865	58,4%	41,0%
Bangladesh	6,261	113	7	71,4%	71,4%
Ivory Coast	5,995	254	113	85,0%	77,0%
Guinea	5,720	549	143	86,7%	74,1%
All countries	143,226	13,403	5,474	64,8%	53,7%

*voluntary returns and spontaneous returns excluded (for definitions in French statistical data see section on returns)

Source: <https://www.immigration.interieur.gouv.fr/Info-ressources/Etudes-et-statistiques/Chiffres-cles-sejour-visas-eloignements-asile-acces-a-la-nationalite/Les-chiffres-cles-de-l-immigration-2021> last accessed 12/10/2023. Last accessed 9/10/2023

LAISSEZ-PASSER CONSULAIRES (LPC)

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2021/ 2020
Laissez-passer demandés (1)	5 811	7 499	8 356	4 685	5 474	+ 16,8%
Laissez-passer obtenus dans les délais utiles (2)	2 966	4 028	5 610	2 619	2 941	+ 12,3%
Laissez-passer obtenus hors délais	147	243	164	139	198	+ 42,4%
Laissez-passer refusés	314	415	237	149	178	+ 19,5%
Demandes sans réponse	2 384	2 813	2 345	1 778	2 157	+ 21,3%
Taux de délivrance dans délai (2)/(1)	51,0%	53,7%	67,1%	55,9%	53,7%	- 2,2 pts

Source: MI-DGEF

Champ: France métropolitaine

SIX PAYS À FORT ENJEU EN TERMES DE COOPÉRATION CONSULAIRE (2021)

	Mesures éloignement prononcées	Mesures éloignement exécutées (*)	Demandes lpc instruites	Taux de reconnaissance de la nationalité	Taux délivrance dans les délais
Algérie	21 452	754	927	51,7 %	5,8 %
Maroc	9 701	844	775	62,3 %	43,1 %
Tunisie	8 446	621	865	58,4 %	41,0 %
Bangladesh	6 261	113	7	71,4 %	71,4 %
Côte d'Ivoire	5 995	254	113	85,0 %	77,0 %
Guinée	5 720	549	143	86,7 %	74,1 %
TOUS PAYS	143 226	13 403	5 474	64,8 %	53,7 %

* Hors aides au départ et départs spontanés

Source: DGEF-DSED

Champ: France métropolitaine

Source: <https://www.immigration.interieur.gouv.fr/Info-ressources/Etudes-et-statistiques/Chiffres-cles-sejour-visas-eloignements-asile-acces-a-la-nationalite/Les-chiffres-cles-de-l-immigration-2021> last accessed 12/10/2023. Last accessed 9/10/2023

The first table focuses on the issuance of *laissez-passer* in time for effecting the return, all nationalities included. The second table shows the issuance rate of *laissez-passer* in time for effecting the return in the case of countries 'à fort enjeu en termes de coopération consulaire', (for which

consular cooperation is an important issue), a criterion whose meaning remains to be questioned. The ‘in-time’ issuance rate varies from 5.8% (Algeria) to 77% (Ivory Coast).

A question about data: in Table 7, we do not know whether the laissez-passer requested include requests for voluntary return. The OFII Annual Report states that in 2021, the OFII has supported 1,120 requests of laissez-passer, 2.03% more than 2020¹⁹.

Key point:

If we consider the nationalities that receive the highest numbers of OtL such as Algerians, Moroccans and Tunisians, we will see that the rate of nationality recognition is high (more than 50%). However, the return rate stays low (less than 10%). This can be established for the year 2021.

Asylum

Table 8 shows the main nationalities of asylum seekers (2019-2022). The main nationalities of asylum seekers do not overlap neither with the main nationalities of migrants to whom an OtL has been issued nor with the main nationalities of returnees (except for Bangladesh and Ivory Coast).

¹⁹ Rapport Annuel 2021, OFII (pp. 49). Available at https://www.ofii.fr/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/HR_RA_OFII_2021_21x297_p3_p114_compressed.pdf

Les dix premiers pays d'origine pour les premières demandes d'asile en GUDA

Nationalité	2019	Nationalité	2021	Nationalité	2022	2022 /2021
Afghanistan	10 258	Afghanistan	16 116	Afghanistan	22 529	+ 39,8 %
Côte d'Ivoire	6 198	Côte d'Ivoire	6 260	Bangladesh	10 549	+ 69,3 %
Bangladesh	5 760	Bangladesh	6 231	Turquie	9 952	+ 99,6 %
Guinée	5 618	Guinée	5 269	Géorgie	8 867	+ 92,8 %
Turquie	5 142	Turquie	4 987	Rép. Dém. Congo	6 724	+ 143,0 %
Albanie	4 657	Albanie	4 915	Guinée	6 175	+ 17,2 %
Géorgie	4 357	Géorgie	4 600	Côte d'Ivoire	5 864	- 6,3 %
Pakistan	4 325	Pakistan	3 735	Albanie	5 650	+ 15,0 %
Nigéria	4 242	Nigéria	3 183	Pakistan	3 746	+ 0,3 %
Comores	4 184	Comores	3 167	Nigéria	2 777	- 12,8 %
Part des 10 nationalités	51,7 %	Part des 10 nationalités	56,0 %	Part des 10 nationalités	60,6%	+ 4,6 pts

Sources : Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, SI-Asile (ANEF)
Champ : France

Table 8 Ten first nationalities of asylum seekers

Source: <https://www.immigration.interieur.gouv.fr/Info-ressources/Etudes-et-statistiques/Chiffres-cles-sejour-visas-eloignements-asile-acces-a-la-nationalite/Les-chiffres-cles-de-l-immigration-2021>

National data about the nationalities of rejected asylum seekers can be found in the OFPRA Annual Reports.

Research at the implementation level shows that the issuance of OtiL after the final rejection of asylum claims does not seem automatic (see page 3).

The local NGOs contracted by the *Direction Départementale de l'Emploi, du Travail et des Solidarités* (DDETS) (that work under the responsibility of the Prefecture) to provide accommodation services to asylum seekers and to support refugees for permanent housing and integration send data to the DDETS every two weeks. Data concerns the total number of people, the percentage of failed asylum seekers, the number of refugees and

the number of available apartments. Data about nationalities, migratory routes and personal stories might be collected but those are not shared with the prefecture²⁰.

Figure 2 shows the evolution of the protection rate (2003-2022).

Sources : OFPRA et CNDA ; calculs DSED
 Champ : France, hors mineurs accompagnés

Figure 2: Evolution of protection rate (2003-2022).

Source: <https://www.immigration.interieur.gouv.fr/Info-ressources/Etudes-et-statistiques/Chiffres-cles-sejour-visas-eloignements-asile-acces-a-la-nationalite/Les-chiffres-cles-de-l-immigration-2021> Last accessed 09/10/2023

²⁰ La préfecture nous demande toutes les deux semaines de remonter des chiffres. Mais ces chiffres, c'est combien il y a de personnes, combien il y a de déboutés qu'on doit expulser, le pourcentage, et combien il y a de réfugiés qui n'ont pas encore trouvé de logement, (...) Et combien il y a d'appartements vides. (Respondent 1, recorded interview).

To my knowledge, data on overstayers are not collected at a national level. The EMN contact point provided a written reply to that question which confirms the unavailability of data on overstayers. However, non-participation of relevant respondents did not allow to dig further into this issue.

Publicly available statistical data at national level do not include the dimension of gender. Data that include a gender dimension are those about immigrants in detention centres, collected by CSOs that provide legal support.

Returns

Table 9 shows national statistical information about returns.

Mouvements	Origine des étrangers	Destination	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2022/2021
Éloignements forcés (A)	Pays tiers	Pays tiers	7 105	8 858	3 329	3 511	5 056	+ 44,0 %
		UE (Réadmissions Schengen, transferts Dublin)	5 615	7 092	3 879	4 638	4 419	- 4,7 %
	Union Européenne		2 957	2 956	1 903	1 942	1 935	- 0,4 %
	Total éloignements forcés (A)		15 677	18 906	9 111	10 091	11 410	+ 13,1 %
Éloignements aidés (B)	Total éloignements aidés (B)		2 070	2 752	1 658	1 570	2 102	+ 33,9 %
Éloignements spontanés (C)	Pays tiers		1 878	1 750	1 259	1 537	1 674	+ 8,9 %
	Union Européenne		332	338	356	205	214	+ 4,4 %
	Total éloignements spontanés* (C)		2 210	2 088	1 615	1 742	1 888	+ 8,4 %
Total éloignements (A) + (B) + (C)			19 957	23 746	12 384	13 403	15 400	+ 14,9 %
Départs volontaires aidés (D)			4 775	2 515	930	1 415	1 263	- 10,7 %
Départs spontanés (E)			5 544	5 143	2 635	2 001	2 766	+ 38,2 %
Total sorties du territoire (A) + (B) + (C) + (D) + (E)			30 276	31 404	15 949	16 819	19 429	+ 15,5 %

Source : DGEF/DSED-DCPAF

Champ : France métropolitaine, tous pays, majeurs

*Mise en œuvre spontanée d'une mesure d'éloignement par la personne concernée

Table 7 Returns and Types of Return (2018-2022)

Source: <https://www.immigration.interieur.gouv.fr/Info-ressources/Etudes-et-statistiques/Chiffres-cles-sejour-visas-eloignements-asile-acces-a-la-nationalite/Les-chiffres-cles-de-l-immigration-2021> Last accessed 09/10/2023

Explanation of categories of return in Table 9:

Éloignements forcés (A) = Forced returns – the majority of returns. It includes EU citizens returned to EU MS, non-EU citizens returned to another EU country (majority), non-EU citizens returned to non-EU countries.

Éloignement aidé (B) = Voluntary return – After the issuance of an OtL, the person has 30 days to leave the territory or 48 hours in case of threat to public order, risk of absconding and/or denial of residence permit for fraud or manifestly unfounded claim. During what can be therefore characterized as a grace period, the person might request support from voluntary return schemes. If the person leaves under a voluntary return scheme, it will be calculated as ‘éloignement aidé’.

Éloignements spontanés (C) = Spontaneous returns – Irregular migrants who have received an OtL and return spontaneously, without coercion and without support from voluntary return schemes.

Départs volontaires aidés (D) = Voluntary return not following an OtL – Irregular migrants who return spontaneously and ask for support from voluntary return schemes, without having received an OtL.

Départs spontanés (E) = Return not following an OtL – Irregular migrants who leave the territory without having received an OtL.

Key fact: In a comparative perspective, it is key to take account that return rates for the case of France include all the different situations explained above (éloignements forcés, éloignement aidés, départs volontaires aidés, éloignement spontanés, départs spontanés).

This study focuses on third country nationals who received an OtL and returned to non-EU countries, including those who have used support from voluntary return schemes, forced returns and those who returned spontaneously. (éloignements forcés de pays tiers à pays tiers + éloignements aidés + éloignements spontanés pays tiers).

The categories of ‘départs spontanés’ and ‘départs volontaires aidés’ are not included because these returnees have not received an OtL. The forced returns (éloignements forcés) of EU nationals and the forced returns of non-EU nationals to an EU MS are not included. The spontaneous return towards EU MSs is not included as well (éloignements spontanés vers UE).

The main data gap concerns the country of return (EU or non-EU) for those who have received support for voluntary return. From the available national data, it is not possible to know the country of destination of these returnees. We will assume that support for voluntary returns concerns non-EU countries.

In the light of the above-mentioned specifications, Table 10 shows the national data on the type of returns which interest this study.

Table 10 Returns of Interest (Forced Return of non-EU nationals to a non-EU country + voluntary returns + spontaneous returns to non-EU countries)

Year	Returns of interest	All returns
2018	11,053	30,276
2019	13,360	31,404
2020	6,246	15,949
2021	6,618	16,819
2022	8,832	19,429

Source: Author's own elaboration based on Table 8. Source: <https://www.immigration.interieur.gouv.fr/Info-ressources/Etudes-et-statistiques/Chiffres-cles-sejour-visas-eloignements-asile-acces-a-la-nationalite/Les-chiffres-cles-de-l-immigration-2021> Last accessed 09/10/2023

Data gap: When we consider only the returns of interest, it is difficult to calculate the return rate, because the Eurostat data on OtL might include OtL issued to non-EU citizens to return to another EU MS.

Regularization: regularization understood as the provision of legal statuses to irregular migrants is not directly connected to OtL, meaning that irregular migrants whose status is regularized might have not received an OtL. The regularization of undocumented workers is the most common case. In France, the so-called 'Vals circular', a non-legally binding administrative regulation, sets principles and procedures to regularize undocumented workers. The Vals circular's importance is diminishing, given that procedures and conditions to regularize workers are evolving in the direction set by the recently adopted law, which focuses on sectors of the labor market 'under pressure'. Interesting cases of regularization are based on health or family grounds. The interview with the head of the migrants' service of one of the major NGOs involved in asylum reception and legal support for migrants and asylum seekers has revealed some patterns of regularization practices. This NGO is one of the four NGOs contracted by the local prefecture to provide services (accommodation, legal counseling and legal support) linked to asylum and irregularity. The head of the migrants' service has described some regularization practices on health or family grounds²¹. According to that person, those are relatively simple cases. Their organization tends to handle more complicated cases such as the regularization on the basis of five years of continued residency. One of the most common cases concerns legal support for those who have lived continuously on the French territory for five years. The

²¹ Les autres moyens de régularisation, ils sont plus faciles. Par exemple, quelqu'un qui serait étranger malade. Donc quelqu'un qui serait malade et qui n'aurait pas la possibilité de se faire soigner dans son pays d'origine. Qui vient en France pour se faire soigner. Ça va être beaucoup plus facile d'être régularisé. Puisqu'on a besoin de consultations médicales, d'attestations qu'on a bien telle maladie. On va à l'OFII, on produit nos pièces et les choses se passent. Et ensuite, préfecture, etc. Mais ça, la moindre association du tissu local peut vous aider à faire régulariser ça. (Respondent 1, recorded interview)

issue at stake concerns the provision of proofs of continuous residency. Those can be either salary slips, since some employers might issue salary slips although workers are undocumented, or certificates of children's enrolment to school²².

²² La loi française dit que si on peut prouver qu'on est depuis 5 ans sur le territoire français de manière irrégulière, de fait, on doit être régularisé, puisqu'on s'est maintenu 5 ans sur le territoire, et donc on a acquis des habitudes de vie privée, de vie familiale, etc. Le problème, c'est d'apporter la preuve des 5 années continues passées sur le territoire. (...) C'est plus facile si on travaille, puisque si on travaille, même si on travaille au noir, il y a un certain nombre d'employeurs qui, même en embauchant au noir, donnent des bulletins de salaire. Ça, c'est une bonne preuve de dire que ça fait 5 ans que je suis sur le territoire, puisque j'ai des bulletins de salaire depuis 5 ans. Donc c'est un bon moyen, mais ça n'a rien à voir si on peut prouver que ça fait 5 ans qu'on a scolarisé son enfant sur le territoire français. On a les certificats de scolarité. Et qu'on a les attestations de la directrice de l'école qui nous a vu récupérer notre enfant tous les soirs pendant 5 ans. Dans ce cas-là, on a la preuve, même si on n'a pas travaillé sur le territoire. (Respondent 1, recorded interview)

Overview draft

Indicator	Data provider	Definition	How data is collected	Frequency	Data dissemination ²³	Corresponding Eurostat indicator (if any)	Comparability with Eurostat indicator
Irregular entry							
refusal of entry (rejection at the border)	Police aux frontières (PAF) -	Rejection at the border if the person has no passport or visa, cannot provide justification of his/her stay, is listed in the SIS, represents a threat to public order, is subjected to a entry ban	N/A	N/A			
Expulsion (I think this category needs more details, what is the difference with returns?)	Police aux frontières (PAF) -	Réadmission – interdiction d'entrée	N/A	N/A	Yearly		
Irregularly staying TCN (entering the category)							
Overstayers	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A		-
Rejected asylum seekers (first instance)	Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, SI-Asile (ANEF) – OFPRA	Negative decision of the OFPRA –	OFPRA	N/A	OFPRA and Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France disseminate data twice a year		
Rejected asylum seekers (final instance)	CNDA Court national du Droit d'Asile -	Negative decisions of the CNDA	CNDA	N/A	OFPRA and Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France disseminate data twice a year		
Irregular staying TCN who received OTL							
Migrants in detention centres	Juge des libertés et de la détention ; Civil Society Organisations	Irregular migrants who have received an OTL	Prefecture - Civil Society Organisations which operate inside	N/A	Civil Society Organizations issue a report every year		

²³ In France, the Ministry of Interior office for immigration and integration statistics (Service statistique ministériel de l'immigration et de l'intégration - DSED) follows the *Code de bonnes pratiques de la statistique européenne*. Every year, a calendar with the date of data release and the type of data released is issued. Data concern residence permits, visas, asylum and returns. See <https://www.immigration.interieur.gouv.fr/Info-ressources/Etudes-et-statistiques/Chiffres-cles-sejour-visas-eloignements-asile-acces-a-la-nationalite/Les-chiffres-2022-publication-annuelle-parue-le-22-juin-2023>

	(Cimade, Groupe SOSSolidarités, forumréfugiés, France terre d'asile, solidarité Mayotte)						
Migrants subject to alternatives to detention	Juge des libertés et de la détention ; Civil Society Organisations (Cimade, Groupe SOSSolidarités, forumréfugiés, France terre d'asile, solidarité Mayotte)	Home custody	Prefecture - Civil Society Organisations which operate inside		Civil Society Organizations issue a report every year		
Exit from the irregularly staying							
Persons returned/readmissions	Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France	See section Returns			Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France disseminate data twice a year		
Forced returns	Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France	See section Returns			Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France disseminate data twice a year		
Voluntary returns	Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France – OFII Office national de l'Immigration et de l'Intégration	See section Returns			Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France disseminate data twice a year		
Voluntary assisted returns	Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France – OFII Office national de l'Immigration et de l'Intégration	See section Returns			Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France disseminate data twice a year		

Returns occurring under a bilateral agreement	N/A See section Cooperation with Third Countries	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A		
Laissez passer requested and obtained (and whether bilateral agreement present)	Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France	Data include the issuance rate in time for enforcing the return and the unanswered requests – no data about the presence of a bilateral agreement			Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France disseminate data twice a year		
Temporary authorization and regularization (flow, stock, renewals)	Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France	Data concern the issuance of permits of stay, not in terms of temporary authorization or regularization	Prefecture	N/A	Ministère de l'intérieur et des outre-mer, Direction Générale des Etrangers en France disseminate data twice a year		

APPENDIX 1: FRANCE'S BI-LATERAL AGREEMENTS LINKED TO READMISSION

COUNTRIES**TYPE OF AGREEMENT, DATE**

EU, plus Iceland, Norway, Switzerland
and the UK

Austria	S 30/11/1962 – S 20/04/2007 (+ S Protocol 30/10/2014) – V 01/07/2015
Belgium	AB, V 16/05/1964
Bulgaria	V 03/02/1997
Croatia	V 18/02/1996
Czechia	S 02/04/1997
Estonia	V 15/04/1999
Germany	V 22/01/1960 – 19/09/2005
Greece	V 01/01/2004
Hungary	V 30/09/1998
Italy	V 01/12/1999
Latvia	V 14/06/1998
Lithuania	V 07/01/2000
Luxembourg	AB, V 16/05/1964
The Netherlands	AB, V 16/05/1964; CP V 01/03/1999
Portugal	V 26/03/1995
Romania	V 12/09/1994; V 01/02/2007; S 12/09/2012
Slovakia	V 02/08/1997
Slovenia	V 14/11/1993
Spain	V 12/04/1989; V 21/12/2003
Sweden	V 29/06/1991
Switzerland	V 01/03/2000
United Kingdom	AA S 06/07/2009; AA S 02/11/2010; C S 28/11/2020
Balkans, Central and eastern European countries, Caucasus	

COUNTRIES**TYPE OF AGREEMENT, DATE**

Armenia	IP S 27/10/2016
Bosnia & Herzegovina	S 20/12/2006; IP V 30/12/2019
Kosovo	V 19/09/2011
Moldova	N
Montenegro	V 25/04/2006
North Macedonia	V 17/06/1999; IP V 06/11/2023
Russia	IP V 22/10/2010
Serbia	IP S 18/11/2009
Maghreb Countries	
Algeria	EL 1984/1994; CP S 25/10/2003
Libya	Framework agreement V 25/07/2007
Morocco	EL 1983/1993; CP V 01/05/2001; C S 07/12/2020 (unaccompanied minors)
Mauritania	N
Tunisia	EL 1984/1994; Pact on joint migration management V 01/07/2009
Other South and East Mediterranean countries	
Egypt	N
Africa	
Benin	Pact on joint migration management V 01/03/2010
Burkina Faso	Pact on joint migration management V 01/06/2011
Cameroon	Pact on joint migration management S 21/05/2009
Cape Verde	Pact on joint migration management V 01/04/2011
Central African Republic	C 26/09/1994
Comoros (Union of The)	Pact on joint migration agreement S 22/07/2019
Congo	C 31/07/1993; Pact on joint migration management V 01/08/2009
Gabon	C 11/03/2002; Pact on joint migration management V 01/09/2008

COUNTRIES

Mali
Mauritius
Niger
Senegal

Latin America and the Caribbean
Argentina
Barbados
Brazil
Chile
Costa Rica
Dominica
Dominican Republic
Ecuador
El Salvador
Guatemala
Guyana
Haiti
Honduras
Mexico
Nicaragua
Panama
Paraguay
St. Lucia
Surinam
Trinidad and Tobago
Uruguay

TYPE OF AGREEMENT, DATE

N
V 01/12/2007; circular migration agreement V 01/09/2010
Tripartite agreement on irregular migration S 13/03/2017
Pact on joint migration management V 01/08/2009
(amendment to the pact: S 25/02/2008)

V 08/02/2002
N
V 24/08/2001
V 08/04/1998
V 18/02/2001
V 01/03/2007
N
V 26/05/2000
V 01/05/1999
V 02/12/1999
N
Framework agreement, V 31/12/2007
V 21/09/2000
V 16/07/1998
S 20/04/1999
V 30/05/1999
V 13/12/1997
S 23/04/2005
S 30/11/2004
N
V 24/07/1997

COUNTRIES	TYPE OF AGREEMENT, DATE
Venezuela	V 30/12/2001
Asia and Oceania	
Afghanistan	S ME 28/09/2002 with UNHCR; V 18/09/2019 (part of the 2017 EU-Afghanistan Cooperation and Partnership Development Agreement)
India	S ME 10/03/2018
Philippines	N
Sri Lanka	N
Vietnam	CP V 17/02/2012

Note: Standard readmission agreements:

- Bilateral readmission agreements which may be signed ('S') or have entered into force ('V');
- Bilateral Implementing Protocols ('IP') to EU readmission agreements (EURAs), concluded between an EU Member State and a non-EU country;
- Agreements concluded between the Benelux countries and a third country (AB).

Non-standard agreements include:

- Police cooperation agreements ('CP') including a clause on the readmission/removal of irregular foreigners;
- Conventions ('C') including a clause on the readmission/removal of irregular foreigners;
- Memoranda of understanding ('ME');
- Administrative arrangements ('AA');
- Provisional agreements ('AP');
- Exchanges of letters ('EL').

Source: Governments' official bulletins and internal documents. Elaborated by Jean-Pierre Cassarino. Available at: <https://www.jeanpierrecassarino.com/datasets/ra/fr/>

Appendix 2: EU-WIDE NON-STANDARD AGREEMENTS LINKED TO READMISSION

EU-wide non-standard agreements linked to readmission

COUNTRIES	MP	CAMM	JWF	JS	SOP	AP	GP	JMD
Afghanistan			02/10/2016; JDMC 26/04/2021					
Armenia	27/10/2011							
Azerbaijan	05/12/2013							
Bangladesh					25/09/2017			
Belarus	13/10/2016							
Cape Verde	05/06/2008							
Cote d'Ivoire					N		01/10/2018	
Ethiopia		11/11/2015				05/02/2018		
Georgia	30/11/2009							
Ghana							N	16/04/2016
Guinea								24/07/2017
India		29/03/2016						
Jordan	09/10/2014							
Mali					N			11/12/2016
Moldova	05/06/2008							
Morocco	07/06/2013							
Niger								03/05/2016
Nigeria		12/03/2015						
The Gambia								16/11/2018
Tunisia	03/03/2014							
Turkey				18/03/2016				

Commented [NA(1): Could you add a column with source link and another column where you assess success of each instrument?

Source: Jean-Pierre Cassarino elaboration of EU documents. Source: <https://www.jeanpierrecassarino.com/datasets/ra/european-union/>

Note: MP=Mobility Partnership; CAMM=Common Agenda on Migration and Mobility; JWF=Joint Way Forward; JDMC= Joint Declaration on Migration Cooperation; JS=Joint Statement; SOP=Standard Operating Procedure for the identification and return of persons without an authorization to stay;

GP=Good Practices for the efficient operation of the return procedure; AP=Admission Procedures for the return of foreign nationals from European Union Member States; JMD=Joint Migration Declaration; N=Negotiations.